

THE EFFECT OF FIBER WAVINESS AS MANUFACTURING DEFECT ON THE FATIGUE LIFE OF CFRP MATERIALS

Susanne Hörrmann^{1,2}, Christoph Viechtbauer^{1,2}, Adi Adumitroaie¹ and Martin Schagerl^{1,2}

¹Institute of Constructional Lightweight Design, Johannes Kepler University Linz
Altenberger Straße 69, Aut-4040 Linz, Austria
Email: martin.schagerl@jku.at, web page: <http://www.ikl.jku.at>

²Christian Doppler Laboratory for Structural Strength Control of Lightweight Constructions, Johannes
Kepler University Linz
Altenberger Straße 69, Aut-4040 Linz, Austria
Email: susanne.hoerrmann@jku.at, web page: <http://www.ikl.jku.at/cd/>

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ABSTRACT

Manufacturing defects in carbon fibre reinforced plastic parts are a balancing act, particularly between safety and cost. Common defects in carbon fibre reinforced plastic parts are voids, porosity, in-plane and out-of-plane layer waviness, inclusions, and even folds of layers. In this work, an automotive non-crimp fabric showing out-of-plane fibre waviness, as it may appear during a high pressure resin transfer moulding process, is investigated. The effect of the manufacturing defect on the compressive static strength and fatigue life of a thin laminate is assessed, considering the influence of different cyclic loading cases.

Static and fatigue tests are performed in order to observe the triggered damage modes, the sequence and interaction of different modes, and the propagation of damage up to the final failure of the sample. The aim of the experimental study is to provide a deep understanding of damage initiation and progression due to the presence of the manufacturing defects.

Prediction of the effects of the defect on the fatigue damage initiation and progression is done, based on detailed meso-scale parametric static FE simulation, supported by the use of non-destructive testing (ultrasonic and microscopy analysis) of the composite material configuration. Correlation between the numerical results and the experimental data is done, in order to validate the experiments, and to assess the predictive capabilities of the numerical modelling.

A manufacturing defect metric is established for the case under investigation and quantitative assessment of the influence of this metric on the compression fatigue life of the material is performed, such that the proposed metric can be used for defining acceptance/rejection criteria for composite parts containing manufacturing defects.

1 INTRODUCTION

Quality is the prerequisite for safety and competitiveness, and the aim of quality management is to achieve a low defect rate [1]. For the automotive industry, with high production rates and strict cost limits, the assessment of manufacturing defects is a topic of great interest. Especially for new production processes and materials, the definition of the accepted levels of the defects induced during manufacturing is necessary. This means that an assessment metric should be defined, and limits of acceptability for the defects can be established. According to these quality measures, the decision on which manufacturing defects are critical (i.e., cause premature failure during service life) and which are acceptable (i.e., not impairing the intended use) can be made during the quality control of the finished part.

In carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) parts there might be a wide variety of defects that can have an influence on the structural response, as shown in [2], where the sources of variability in aircraft structures are studied. Common manufacturing features in CFRP parts are, for example, voids, porosity, in-plane and out-of-plane layer waviness, inclusions, fibres clustering, and even folds of

layers. Regarding the out-of-plane waviness, various causes of the occurrence of this kind of defect during manufacturing are discussed in [3].

The compression response of laminated composites featuring out-of-plane waviness as a result of different manufacturing methods was previously investigated, focusing mainly on the static strength and stiffness [4, 5]. The influence on fatigue damage was investigated mainly for glass epoxy laminates, which are used in wind turbine blades [6].

In this work, a Carbon/Epoxy automotive non crimp fabric showing out-of-plane fibre waviness, as it may appear during a high pressure resin transfer moulding (RTM) process, is investigated. The effect of the manufacturing defect on the static strength, residual stiffness and fatigue life of a unidirectional (UD) laminate is assessed, considering different static and cyclic loading cases. The focus of this research work is mainly the *compressive* on-axis loading, since it is expected that the induced out-of-plane waviness has the highest influence for this loading case [4].

In section 2 of the paper, the manufacturing feature in the form of out-of-plane waviness is characterized, according to its possible geometry configuration, as resulting from the RTM process.

Then, the experimental investigation on the compressive static strength and fatigue life, with focus on damage initiation and progression is presented in section 3. The influence of defect geometry on different fracture patterns is analysed from the results of the experimental program.

In section 4 a parametric meso-scale FE model is developed based on the geometry definition in section 2, in order to investigate the influence of the defect geometry on damage initiation, and to support the experimental observations presented in section 3.

2 DEFECT CHARACTERIZATION

In most of the published papers dealing with the influence of the layer waviness on the mechanical performances of the material, the waviness is usually quantified by the wave severity, i.e., the ratio of wave amplitude over wavelength, or the maximum misalignment angle [4, 5]. Thus, usually sine waves of a defined amplitude and wavelength are considered for describing and quantifying the out-of-plane waviness. Then, if experimental investigation is part of the research project, a means of introducing and controlling the magnitude of the desired defect has to be considered. For example, copper rods are used in [5] in order to introduce the waviness.

For the investigation presented in this paper, specimens with a constant nominal thickness are produced in a high pressure RTM process out of six unidirectional layers of a non-crimp fabric. Out-of-plane fibre waviness is simulated by inserting two polymer rods (with a diameter of 0.5 mm) transverse to the fibre direction, between the top and bottom outer layers of the UD laminate (see Fig. 1). In this way, also considering the influence of the manufacturing process, a half wave waviness results in the four inner layers between the polymer rods.

However, during RTM processing, the distance c between the locations of the manufacturing defects is not constant, the configuration of the defect at the laminate level is a function of the distance c , or of the corresponding angle α , as presented in Fig. 1(a). The misalignment angle α was preferred and selected in this work as a quantitative measure of the level of the defect. The reason for this selection is that the angle α can be easier measured, resulting thus in a more accurate metric compared to alternative options presented in the literature, such as the maximum fibre angle, the waviness amplitude, or the length of the resin-zone.

For the case of the metric α selected for this work, a high value (close to 90°) means that the top and bottom manufacturing perturbations are close to each other along axial (fibre) direction, while a low value means that the two perturbations are far away from each other.

The defect metric α of each specimen is assessed through optical microscopy and digital image analysis (see Fig. 1(b)). The geometry of the defect at both free edges is measured, and the mean values of c and α are calculated for each specimen; the resulting range of α for all specimens is between 20° and 88° . The optical microscopy and ultrasonic pre-test inspections are also performed in order to assure that no other pre-existing form of damage is present (for example, air voids or delamination due to manufacturing, or edge cracks due to sample cutting).

Figure 1: a) Schematic cross section of the laminate, featuring induced fibre waviness;
b) Appendant microscopy image.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

3.1 Specimen geometry and preparation

Test specimens are water jet cut out of composite plates with introduced layer waviness as described in section 2. Compressive tests are performed according to ASTM D 3410 – 03, which is used for the determination of compressive properties of polymer matrix composite materials [7]; the gauge length of 25 mm is selected, which is the maximum recommended by the standard, in order to avoid stress perturbation due to gripping in the defect area, and for better inspection conditions. Global buckling of the specimen is precluded, since the critical buckling length according to ASTM D 3410 – 03 is 27.06 mm at the maximum static compressive load of the used test rig. The specimen geometry is depicted in Fig. 2.

For proper load introduction, aluminium tabs with a length of 50 mm and a thickness of 2 mm are bonded on the specimens. Aluminium tabs can reduce unwanted heating of the specimen due to cyclic loading, and are easy to manufacture. A bonding device was constructed in-house, which assures a constant bonding pressure and perfect alignment of the tabs. The 3M epoxy adhesive DP 490 is used, since it has high shear strength and can be cured at 65°C, which is below the glass temperature of the resin.

Figure 2: Specimen geometry in mm.

3.2 Test set up and procedure

The test equipment includes a 25 kN servo-hydraulic testing machine equipped with hydraulic grips. For the alignment of the specimens between the upper and lower grips, an alignment device was designed in-house (see Fig. 3), which allows only axial movement of the grips. In this way, specimen bending and torsion are prevented.

Figure 3: Clamping and alignment device.

To observe stiffness degradation, the global strain is evaluated using the displacement of the hydraulic load cylinder, while local strains at the location of the defect are measured with strain gauges applied on both sides of the specimen. Both local and global strain measurements are performed, in order to double-check both the validity of the experimental data, and the fact that the location of the induced defect corresponds to the location of damage development. Some of the strain gauges failed before completion of the tests due to fatigue loading induced in the gauges themselves; however, the measurements before the failure of the gauges could be used to detect local bending due to the defect and to verify the global strain measurement.

The test procedure for studying the influence of the compression cyclic loading on the fatigue life of the material featuring the manufacturing defect under investigation (see section 1 and 2) comprises the following steps:

First, static compression tests are performed to determine the static strength of the specimens. They were performed under displacement controlled conditions, with a machine cross-head speed of 0.267 mm/min.

Then, compression-compression (C-C, stress ratio $R=100$) and tension-compression (T-C, stress ratio $R=-1$) at five different load levels are carried out with at least two tests per load level. The load ratio $R=100$ for the C-C tests was selected to exclude the possibility of small tensile loading while unloading from the compression load, due to inertia in the feedback control system of the testing machine.

The fatigue tests were performed under load control conditions, having applied sinusoidal-type loading at ambient temperature and a frequency of 5 or 10 Hz. The frequency was raised after initial tests, since no significant hysteretic heating of the specimens could be measured. The specimen temperature was measured before and during the test using an infrared thermometer and it was found constant, around $24 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$.

3.3 Experimental results

Besides the recorded data, the experimental observations also concerned the following aspects of progressive damage and failure under compressive cyclic loading: the moment (number of cycles), location and damage mode for *damage initiation*; damage modes for the *damage progression*; the moment and the dominant damage mode for the *failure* (defined as fracture) of the specimen.

For all tested specimens, the location of failure (final fracture line) connects the two induced perturbation points, also passing through the inflection point Y of the inner layers (see Fig. 1(a)); this observation is consistent with previous experimental observations during compression static tests [5, 8].

For specimens featuring the waviness misalignment angle into the range I: $25^\circ < \alpha < 70^\circ$, damage initiation and progression is according to the following sequence: matrix cracking in the resin zones; delamination nucleation of the outer layers due to matrix cracking in the resin zones; further delamination of the outer layers due to the fact that the not supported outer layers are pressed outwards; fibre fracture of the outer layers; then, the inner layers are bended at the locations of highest misalignment fibre angle in the inner layers; finally, this bending loading triggers shear fracture and formation of kink bands in the inner layers; the kink band can span the whole distance between the two induced perturbation points, or can appear in only one or two inner layers, while the rest of the inner layers fail through the shear fracture. One example of this kind of failure is presented in Fig. 4(a).

However, for specimens featuring the waviness misalignment angle into the range II: $70^\circ < \alpha < 90^\circ$ (i.e., the induced defects are close to each other along the axial direction, Fig. 4(b)), the sequence of damage is different: there is no indication that damage is a progressive sequence of different modes, as in the previous case. Matrix cracking in the resin zones does not happen first, and consequently, the nucleation and progressive delamination of the outer layers does not take place (see Fig. 4(b)). Final failure occurs through two lines of shear fracture, each of them connecting the location of the induced perturbation with the corresponding point of the highest misalignment fibre angle (point Y in Fig. 1(a)). The two fracture lines intersect around the centre of the inner layers; the consequence is the formation of delamination between the inner layers, which does not happen in the previous case of low α values.

The above observations proved to be consistent for both C-C and T-C fatigue tests, as well as for the case of static compression.

Figure 4: Fracture under cyclic compression loading: a) range I, b) range II

3.4 Experimental data processing

The displacement and strain data collected, respectively, from the piston/strain gauge measurements, is further processed with MATLAB in order to obtain the stiffness degradation curves: for each loading cycle, the degraded elastic modulus is calculated based on the differences between the peak values of displacement/strain, under constant amplitude cyclic stress conditions; the cross-section of the specimens is assumed to be constant. The stiffness of the test rig was initially measured with a steel specimen and was taken into account.

Stiffness degradation curves of specimens containing the induced defect, tested under C-C and T-C loading in fibre direction, show no reduction of Young's modulus until fracture ("sudden death"), as depicted in Fig. 5. This suggests the fact that, from the axial stiffness reduction point of view, the material under study (featuring manufacturing defect in form of the out-of-plane layer waviness along axial direction, see Fig. 1) behaves similar to the material without manufacturing defect: no stiffness degradation along axial (fibre) direction, followed by sudden death, as previously shown in [9, 10]. The back-to-back strain gauge measurements differ constantly by about 6%; this is due to the induced local bending by the presence of the fibre waviness defects.

Figure 5: Axial stiffness curve of a C-C specimen.

The same conclusion is reached regarding evaluation of the experimental data in transverse direction: there is no stiffness degradation along transverse to fibre direction, regardless the applied loading case (T-T, T-C, or C-C), for the material featuring waviness manufacturing defects along fibres direction (as described in Fig. 1); the transvers stiffness degradation curves look similar to those for axial stiffness degradation. Here, the finding is opposed to the results of another experimental program [10], where it was concluded that, for the case of the glass/epoxy material systems investigated, there is transverse stiffness reduction in the UD layers due to cyclic loading. The cause for this different outcome of the experimental results presented in the current paper, and those presented in [10], might be multiple: the fatigue stiffness degradation behaviour of the polymeric matrix used in the two experimental works is different; or, the fatigue transverse stiffness degradation behaviour of the two composite material systems (Carbon/Epoxy in this work, and Glass/Epoxy in [10]) is different. However, for the purpose of the current work (i.e., investigation of the effect of manufacturing defects on the fatigue behaviour of the composite material), it is expected that the induced waviness along fibre direction has little or no effect on the material behaviour along transverse to fibres direction. Further investigation on this assumption has to be done.

It has to be mentioned that, while the above stiffness degradation conclusions have been obtained from experimental data on UD material (the laminate contains layers all of the same orientation), the situation is different for a multi-directional (MD) laminated composite, according to other experimental investigations [9]. Here, usually a transverse stiffness reduction of individual layers inside of the laminate has to be considered, which is due to progressive matrix cracks in the off-axis layers; this transverse cracks multiplication process translates into a reduction of the transverse stiffness of the layer, as well as of the layer shear stiffness. However, this cracks-based layer stiffness degradation can take place only for the layers inside of a laminate.

Next, the influence of the induced defect on the fatigue axial strength of the UD material is analysed based on the interpretation of the experimental data. Thus, the dependence of fatigue life (number of cycles at failure) on the applied stress level and angle α is evaluated. It is assumed that the fatigue behaviour of the material without manufacturing defects follows Basquin's power law:

$$N/N_e = (\sigma_{max} / \sigma_{max,e})^k \quad (1)$$

where σ_{max} is the maximum value of the applied cyclic stress, and N is the fatigue life (number of cycles to failure) for the applied cyclic stress level. Regarding the endurance limit of the material (subscript e in the above equation), this is conventionally defined as the maximum value of the applied cyclic stress $\sigma_{max,e}$ for which the material withstands a number $N_e = 2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles.

With an assumed slope-related parameter k of the S-N curve of the material without defect, the endurance limit $\sigma_{max,e}$ is calculated for each specimen with defect (as in Fig. 6(a)), in order to extract the correlation between the endurance limit of the specimens with induced defect and the defect

angle α . The parameter k for a UD laminate without defect, in fibre direction, is taken as $k=25$, according to [10]. The same value of k is assumed for both T-C and C-C load cases; this assumption is based on the fact that specimens tested under both load cases show similar damage evolution and failure modes (see section 3.3); the influence of the tension part of loading on damage seems to be negligible. The validity of the assumptions of the same k value for different defect configurations (different angle α), and different load cases (C-C and T-C), has yet to be verified.

The blue points in Fig. 6 are from specimens featuring defects tested under T-C loading, and the red points are from specimens tested under C-C loading. The correlation $\sigma_{max,e} = \sigma_{max,e}(\alpha)$ can be approximated by a quadratic polynomial, that features a minimum at about $\alpha = 45^\circ$, as presented in Fig. 6(b). The approximated polynomial is about the same for T-C and C-C specimens, therefore only one is depicted here.

Figure 6: a) Calculation of endurance limit for all specimens; b) correlation of endurance limit to α .

4 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

4.1 FE model

A parametric finite element study of the material with manufacturing defect is performed in ABAQUS, according to the characterization presented in section 2. The length of the resin-zone is assumed to be equal on each side of polymer rods used to simulate the manufacturing waviness defect, and the inserted polymer rods are considered of circular cross-section. Since the specimen width is large compared to its thickness and the defect geometry is approximately constant over the width, the model is assumed to be in a plane strain state. The model is discretized with 8-node biquadratic plane strain elements with reduced integration (CPE8R), of an average element size of 0.05 mm.

Three different materials are defined, one for the CFRP, one for the resin-zones and one for the polymer rods, as depicted in Fig. 7. Due to lack of material data regarding the polymer rod insertions, it is assumed that the modulus of elasticity of them is lower than that of the resin (see Table 1). The CFRP was modelled using both orthotropic and isotropic material models; however, in the orthotropic model the stress distribution shows discontinuities, due to discontinuity in the orientation assigned to the material. Therefore, only results of the isotropic calculation are shown here.

Figure 7: FE model – Material assignment and loading.

Elastic constant		Value
E_{CFRP}	[GPa]	128
E_{resin}	[GPa]	3.4
$E_{inclusion}$	[GPa]	1
ν	[1]	0.3*

*for all materials the same

Table 1: Elastic properties for the FE model

The model is loaded with a 10 N compression load, applied at the right end, by the use of MPC's, as depicted in Fig. 7. Displacement in y-direction at the specimen ends are suppressed, in order to avoid the lateral global bending of the specimen; in the experiment this is achieved by the use of the alignment device, as described in section 3.2.

4.2 Stress analysis

In a static linear elastic analysis, the locations of the highest stresses are evaluated in order to detect possible locations of damage initiation. Therefore, maximum and minimum principal stresses are examined; example plots of maximum and minimum principal stresses are presented in Fig. 8, for $\alpha = 66.19^\circ$. The highest tensile stresses occur at locations (A) in the resin-zones, the highest compressive stresses in the outer layers occur at locations (B), while the highest compressive stresses in the inner layers occur at locations (C), and are slightly lower those in the outer layers.

Figure 8: a) Max. and b) Min. principal stresses in defect area.

According to this analysis, cracks might occur first in the resin-zones due to high local tensile stresses (mode I crack initiation), since this is the preferred fracture mode for delamination initiation [11]; then, the initial cracks in the resin zones grow as delamination of the outer layers,. At locations (B) and (C), fatigue fibre fractures might occur due to higher compressive stresses, this leading to the final fracture of the specimen.

4.3 Influence of defect configuration on damage

The parametric FE model is used to investigate the influence of the manufacturing defect metric (i.e., angle α in Fig. 1(a)) on the stress distribution around the induced layer waviness. Therefore, the distance between the inclusions c is varied at constant wave severity. Nine different α angle between 25° and 85.8° are evaluated.

The resulting maximum principal stresses in the resin-zones and minimum principal stresses in inner and outer layers are listed in Table 2.

Angle α [°]	Distance c [mm]	Max. principal stress (A) [10^{-2} MPa]	Min. principal stress (B) [MPa]	Min. principal stress (C) [MPa]
85.8	0.5	3.24	1.71	1.36
82.4	1.8	3.32	1.71	1.37
66.2	6.0	3.64	1.72	1.46
56.5	9.0	3.76	1.74	1.51
48.6	12.0	3.79	1.75	1.52
45.0	13.6	3.81	1.76	1.51
37.1	18.0	3.80	1.79	1.47
29.5	24.0	3.67	1.82	1.41
25.0	29.2	3.64	1.83	1.41

Table 2: Max. and min. principal stresses for each angle α

In Fig. 9, the variation of principal stress with the defect angle α is presented. It is found that at locations (A) and (C) the highest stresses occur with tendency towards $\alpha \approx 45^\circ$, while at lower and higher angles the stress concentrations are reduced. At location B, the highest stress concentrations occur at the smallest angle α , which means for the largest distance c in Fig. 1. At all locations, the lowest stresses occur at $\alpha \rightarrow 90^\circ$, where c is almost 0.

Figure 9: Variation of max. and min. principle stresses (FE) with the defect angle α .

Based on the fact that damage is initiated at stress concentrations, and higher stress levels initiate damage earlier during the cycling loading, leading thus to a reduction of the endurance limit, the better comparison between the experimental data in Fig. 6(b) and the numerical results presented in this section has actually to be done by the inversion of the results presented in Fig. 9 (i.e., $1/\sigma_{\text{max. principal}}$ and $1/\sigma_{\text{min. principal}}$), as depicted in Fig. 10:

Figure 10: Variation of $1 / \text{max. and min. principle stresses (FE)}$ with the defect angle α .

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

A correlation between the defect geometry and the fatigue limit of T-C and C-C tests was found experimentally, as described in section 3. In section 4, the correlation between the geometry of defect and static stress concentrations was studied, based on linear FE analysis.

For lower defect angle α , local bending induced by the defect is antisymmetric around the inflection point of the waviness (point Y in Fig. 1). Therefore, all experimentally fatigue limits are lower than in the case of symmetric defect geometry obtained for high $\alpha \rightarrow 90^\circ$ (see Fig. 6(b)); this is in agreement with the fact that all numerically evaluated stress concentration levels are higher for this case of lower α values (Fig. 9). The minimum of the experimental fatigue limit in Fig. 6(b) is at $\alpha \approx 45^\circ$, which correlates to the inverse of the static stress levels at locations (A) and (C) in Fig. 10. These observations are also in agreement with the 45° direction for shear fracture under compression loading. This minimum is not maintained at location (B) in Fig. 8(b), since it is outside of the induced waviness area.

The locations of static stress concentration areas (Fig. 8) might be an indication for the locations of fatigue damage initiation; moreover, the sign of the static stresses in the concentration areas give indication on the modes of damage initiation. Thus, damage of specimens with $25^\circ < \alpha < 70^\circ$ was initiated by matrix cracks in the resin-zones (see section 3.3). From that it can be concluded that in this range of α , the max. principal stresses in the resin-zones is predominant.

The experimentally obtained highest fatigue limits are reached for $\alpha \rightarrow 90^\circ$ (Fig. 6(b)), which corresponds to maximum values of all numerically evaluated inverse static stress concentration levels (Fig. 10). This is reasonable, since the geometry of the specimen is symmetric for the case of α angle close to 90° , and no local bending is induced by the defect.

For specimens with $\alpha > 70^\circ$, the tensile stress concentration in the resin-zones (A) either does not initiate matrix cracking (see Fig. 8(a) and 9(a)), or the symmetric configuration of the defect area does not allow for the further crack propagation in form of delamination of the outer layers. Thus, the compressive stresses at locations (B) and (C) in the CFRP (Fig. 8(a) and 9(b)) lead directly to shear fracture of the samples, under the cyclic application of the far field compressive loading.

The locations of the calculated minimal principle stresses in the CFRP layers (points (B) and (C) in Fig. 8(b)), together with the induced waviness inflection point Y in Fig. 1, correspond to the direction of the final compression fracture during fatigue experiments. Therefore, it can be inferred that the static results of the FE analysis give indication on the fracture location and mode for the undulated CFRP layers.

Based on the experimental results obtained during this work, it can be concluded, that the investigated out-of-plane waviness has a severe influence on the fatigue life of the specimen under C-C and T-C loading. Under the considered assumption of constant slope parameter k (see section 3.4 and Fig. 6), a correlation function between the reduction of the fatigue life and the defect angle α was found, which has a maximum at $\alpha \approx 45^\circ$; here, the fatigue life is reduced by approximately 50 %.

Based on above discussion and interpretation of the obtained experimental and numerical results, it can be concluded that the static FE analysis can give indication on the fatigue damage and failure of the material under investigation; this is even without accurate material input data, without considering the CFRP orthotropic behaviour, and, the most important in terms of the input data, without requiring the experimentally expensive fatigue material characterization. It is nevertheless true that these indicators come after a thoroughly understanding of the failure behaviour of the material.

It should be noticed that the severity of the calculated stress concentration levels is much smaller than the corresponding difference in the fatigue limits. This might be due to inherent small differences in the wave severity at different α angle, or even due to inaccurate material input data. It is also possible that the calculation model of the endurance limit (section 3.4, Fig. 6(a)) brings its own error, due to the assumption of constant slope k for every angle α and load cases; as mentioned in section 3.4, the level of accuracy and the range of applicability of this assumption has yet to be investigated.

As further research, the influence of the manufacturing defect in form of out-of-plane waviness on the fatigue life under T-T loading is planned. Then, the influence of other types of defects is to be considered.

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